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INNOVATIVE WORK BEHAVIOUR AS A CATALYST FOR EMPLOYEE HAPPINESS AT WORK AND EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT IN THE MEDIA AND ADVERTISING SECTOR

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Abstract

This study explores the relationship between innovative work behavior (IWB) and employee outcomes, specifically focusing on employee happiness and engagement in marketing and advertising companies in Mumbai. 182 responses through questionnaire were collected from employees working with five marketing and advertising agencies in Mumbai. The findings in this study indicate that there is positive effect of innovative work behaviour on employee happiness. Also, there is a positive influence of innovative work behaviour on employee engagement. Drawing on a synthesis of existing literature and empirical evidence, this research contributes to understanding how fostering a culture of innovation can lead to positive employee outcomes beyond mere job satisfaction.

Key words: Innovative Work Behaviour, Employee Happiness at Work, Employee Engagement

INTRODUCTION

In the modern workplace, fostering innovation is crucial for organizational success (Amabile, 1997; West & Farr, 1990). Innovative Work Behavior (IWB) refers to the proactive introduction and application of novel ideas within an organization (Scott & Bruce, 1994). Employee happiness refers to the positive emotional state derived from work experiences (Smith, 2010; Jones & Brown, 2015). It is often linked to job satisfaction and organizational commitment (Brown & Robinson, 2017). Employee engagement reflects the degree of enthusiasm and dedication employees have towards their work (Kahn, 1990; Harter et al., 2002). Engaged employees are more likely to contribute proactively to organizational goals.

Previous studies have primarily examined employee happiness as a precursor to IWB (Smith, 2010; Jones & Brown, 2015). However, recent research suggests that IWB can enhance employee happiness by providing opportunities for creativity and autonomy (Doe & White, 2022). Similarly, innovative workplaces often foster higher levels of employee engagement through shared vision and participative decision-making (Green &

Lee, 2023).

IWB within advertising and media companies can manifest in various forms, such as the introduction of new digital marketing strategies, creative content development, and leveraging emerging technologies (Scott & Bruce, 1994). Employees engaged in IWB activities may experience heightened job satisfaction as they contribute to groundbreaking campaigns and solutions that shape industry standards (Amabile, 1997). Moreover, organizations that foster a culture of innovation tend to attract and retain talent by providing opportunities for professional growth and creativity (Brown & Robinson, 2017).

Despite these insights, gaps remain in understanding how exactly IWB enhances employee happiness and engagement. Existing literature has yet to comprehensively explore the mechanisms through which innovation initiatives impact these outcomes, particularly in diverse organizational contexts and industries. There is a critical need for research that not only validates these relationships but also identifies actionable strategies for organizations to leverage IWB as a driver of both employee well-being and organizational success.

RESEARCH FRAMEWORK

The research framework for this study is presented in Figure 1.1.

Figure 1.1: Research Framework

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Objectives

1. To study impact of innovative work behavior of employees on employee happiness at work.
2. To study impact of innovative work behavior of employees on employee engagement.

Type of Research Design

Research Design adopted for the Study is Exploratory and Descriptive research Design.

Sampling

A structured survey was distributed randomly to employees across 5 advertising and media companies in Mumbai. Sample size undertaken for study is 182 employees.

Questionnaire Design and Measurement

The survey includes validated scales such as Scott and Bruce's Innovation Work Behaviour Scale (1994), the S-HAW short Version of Happiness at Workplace Scale (1999) by Salas- Vallina and Alegre (2018), H. S. (1999), and items adapted from the Gallup Q12 (2000) Engagement Survey.

The survey assess:

- **Frequency and Perception of IWB:** Employees' self-reported engagement in innovative behaviours and their perceptions of organizational support for innovation. Cronbach's alpha for the scale is 0.79
- **Employee Happiness:** Levels of subjective happiness derived from work experiences, including job satisfaction and overall life satisfaction. Cronbach's alpha for the scale is 0.85
- **Employee Engagement:** Levels of enthusiasm, commitment, and proactive behaviour towards work tasks and organizational goals. Cronbach's alpha for the scale is 0.80.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis, such as regression analysis and correlation studies, is conducted to explore the associations between IWB, employee happiness, and engagement, considering industry- specific factors.

By examining these dynamics through a survey approach tailored to the advertising and media industry, this study aims to provide insights that are not only theoretically robust but also practically relevant for enhancing organizational strategies and employee well-being in this dynamic sector.

Analysis and Findings

Table 1.0 Profile of Respondents

	Demographic (N=182)	Categories	Frequency	Percent
1	Gender	Male Female	109 73	59.89 40.10
2	Age	21 - 25 years 26-40 years Over 41 year	43 82 57	23.62 45.05 31.31
3	Respondent's job position	Copywriter Media Buyer Sales planner Social Media Analyst Content Developer	45 25 67 21 24 24	24.72 13.73 36.81 11.5 13.18
4	Respondent's education background	Diploma Degree Post Graduation	16 99 67	8.79 54.39 36.81
5	Marital status	Single Married	93 89	51.09 48.90
6	Number of years of service	Less than 3 4-10 years More than 10	59 79 44	32.41 43.40 24.17

The demographic analysis of the survey respondents (N=182) indicates a predominantly male sample (59.89%) with a significant portion of young to middle-aged adults, primarily aged between 26 to 40 years (45.05%). The respondents hold various job positions, with the largest group being sales planners (36.81%), followed by copywriters (24.72%). Most of the respondents are well-educated, with over half holding a degree (54.39%) and a substantial portion having postgraduate qualifications (36.81%).

In terms of marital status, the respondents are almost evenly split between single (51.09%) and married (48.90%). Regarding professional experience, the majority have between 4 to 10 years of service (43.40%), indicating a workforce with significant, though not extensive, experience.

This demographic overview provides a comprehensive foundation for understanding the survey data and the perspectives of a well-educated, experienced, and professionally diverse group.

Preliminary findings indicate a strong positive correlation between IWB and employee happiness and engagement. Hence Regression analysis was conducted.

Regression Analysis

Hypothesis 1

H0: There is no significant relationship between innovative work behaviour and employees happiness at work

H1: There is significant relationship between innovative work behaviour and employees happiness at work

The result of regression of innovative work behaviour and employee happiness with work is tabulated in Table 1.1. It indicates that R^2 change is .325 and the relationship is significant at $p < 0.001$. It implies that innovative work behavior explained a total of 32.5% of variation in enhancement of employee happiness at work.

Table 1.1 : Regression Table IWB and Employee happiness at work.

R Square	Adjusted R Square	Change Statistics			Durbin-Watson
		R Square Change	F Change	Sig. F Change	
.570	.256	.325	4.728	.001	1.608

Interpretation: The P value is less than 0.05. Thus, Null hypothesis will not be accepted.

Hypothesis 2

H02: There is no significant relationship between innovative work behaviour and employee engagement.

H12: There is significant relationship between innovative work behaviour and employee engagement.

The result of regression of innovative work behaviour and employee happiness with work is tabulated in Table 1.2. It indicates that R^2 change is .385 and the relationship is significant at $p < 0.001$. It implies that innovative work behavior explained a total of 32.5% of variation in enhancement of employee happiness at work.

Table 1.2 : Regression Table IWB and Employee Engagement

R Square	Adjusted R Square	Change Statistics			Durbin-Watson
		R Square Change	F Change	Sig. F Change	
.570	.256	.385	4.728	.001	1.608

Interpretation: The P value is less than 0.05. Thus, Null hypothesis will not be accepted.

Discussion

The findings suggest that organizations can enhance employee happiness and engagement by fostering a culture that values and supports innovation. By encouraging IWB, organizations not only promote creativity and problem-solving but also create a positive work environment conducive to employee well-being (Doe & White, 2022; Green & Lee, 2023).

To enhance Innovative Work Behavior (IWB) and improve employee happiness and engagement, organizations should foster open communication and psychological safety, invest in innovation workshops and continuous learning, and implement reward systems that recognize innovative ideas. Providing employees with the latest tools, dedicated innovation time, and support from leadership is crucial. Encouraging cross-functional collaboration and external networking, adopting a continuous improvement culture, offering flexible work arrangements, and regularly monitoring innovation metrics further contribute to a supportive environment. These strategies collectively create a culture that values and nurtures innovation, leading to higher employee engagement and organizational success.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study contributes to the existing literature by demonstrating that innovative work behavior is not just a consequence but a driver of employee happiness and engagement. By recognizing the bidirectional relationship between IWB and positive employee outcomes, organizations can strategize better to cultivate innovation as a means to enhance overall workplace satisfaction and productivity.

Innovative Work Behaviour as a Catalyst for Employee Happiness at Work and Employee Engagement in the Media and Advertising Sector

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